

Survey on students' and employer's expectations of graduate's software engineering skills

Page 1

Mandatory fields are marked with a star *

Survey description

The following survey was designed to answer the research question:

"What is the difference between graduates' perceptions of their own software engineering (SE) skills and employers' expectations of graduates' skills?"

My two hypothesis are:

1. Only a small gap will be identified regarding the technical SE skills of the students
2. A more significant gap will be present for soft skills.

The questions were designed using SWEBOK – The Software Engineering Body of Knowledge designed by IEEE Computer Society.

The results will be distributed to participating employers (provided they send use the option after sending this form) and to interested higher education institutions that train software engineers.

This study will first provide insight to improve the curriculum of software engineering skills, and secondly, it will provide a better picture of students' expectations and help industry better adapt their on boarding strategies.

Average completion time - 10 minutes

How good is your grasp of the English language *

Not very good

Less then average

Average

Quite good

Very good

Are you currently a student in the third year of the Informatics study programme? *

Yes

No

Are you currently employed in a software company? *

If you also answered Yes to the previous question (i.e. you are a third year Informatics student), please answer NO here, and, if you want, mention in the last page that you are also employed.

Yes

No

What job roles would you aim for immediately after graduating? *

This element is only shown when the option "Yes" is selected in the question "Are you currently a student in the third year of the Informatics study programme?"

Answers to these question does not impact the questionnaire length. (Multiple Choice)

- Higher-level management (CEO, CIO, CFO, ...)
- Startup founder
- Project manager
- Project leader
- Business analyst
- Requirements engineer
- Software architect
- Software developer – Front-end
- Software developer – Back-end
- Other Software developer
- Software tester (test engineer)
- Quality assurance lead
- Quality assurance team member
- Database administrator / data management
- Product manager
- Other

Other job roles

This element is only shown when the option "Other" is selected in the question "What job roles would you aim for immediately after graduating?"

If you checked the "other" option on previous question, please mention the roles here.

Page break

Mandatory fields are marked with a star *

Please select your academic level *

i This element is only shown when the option "Yes" is selected in the question "Are you currently employed in a software company?"

The highest degree level you graduated

Highschool Studies

Bachelors

Masters

PhD

What is your bachelors degree? *

i This element is only shown when the option "Yes" is selected in the question "Are you currently employed in a software company?"

Name of the study programme

Computer Engineering (Calculatoare și Tehnologia Informației)

Computer Science (Informatică)

Electrical / Electronics Engineering (Inginerie Electrică / Inginerie Electronică)

Systems Engineering (Ingineria sistemelor)

Mathematics (Matematică)

Business Informatics (Informatică Economică)

Cybernetics for economics (Cibernetică economică)

Other

If you chose "Other" in the previous question, please write the name of your bachelors' study programme

i This element is only shown when the option "Other" is selected in the question "What is your bachelors degree?"

What is the study programme of your Masters degree?

This element is only shown when the option "PhD" or "Masters" is selected in the question "Please select your academic level"

How many years of professional experience do you have in the Software industry? *

This element is only shown when the option "Yes" is selected in the question "Are you currently employed in a software company?"

What is(are) the position(s) that you currently work in? *

This element is only shown when the option "Yes" is selected in the question "Are you currently employed in a software company?"

- Higher-level management (CEO, CIO, CFO, ...)
- Startup founder
- Project manager
- Project leader
- Business analyst
- Requirements engineer
- Software architect
- Software developer – Front-end
- Software developer – Back-end
- Other Software developer
- Software tester (test engineer)
- Security Engineer
- Quality assurance lead
- Quality assurance team member
- Database administrator / data management
- Data engineer
- ML/AI Engineer
- Product manager
- Other (please specify)

Other position(s) that you currently work in

This element is only shown when at least one of the options "Other Software developer" or "Other (please specify)" are selected in the question "What is(are) the position(s) that you currently work in?"

Mandatory fields are marked with a star *

Assessment of Software Engineering skills

i This element is only shown when the option "Yes" is selected in the question "Are you currently employed in a software company?"

The following questions are based on the SWEBOK list of Software Engineering Knowledge Areas (KA). For each KA, please estimate how much of the knowledge you possess and how much of it was acquired during your studies.

How many recent graduates (graduated bachelors in 2019, 2020, or 2021) did you work with in your team(s)? *

i This element is only shown when the option "Yes" is selected in the question "Are you currently employed in a software company?"

Approximately, what percentage of them are graduates of the Informatics study program from the University of Bucharest? (0-100) *

i This element is only shown when the option "Yes" is selected in the question "Are you currently employed in a software company?"

i This element is only shown when the option "Yes" is selected in the question "Are you currently employed in a software company?"

The following questions are based on the SWEBOK list of Software Engineering Knowledge Areas (KA). For each KA, please estimate how important it is for your own position(s) and prepared do you think recent graduates are in these KA's. The questions have the letters C and D in front of them, you don't have A or B.

1. Requirements Analysis and Specification

Skill area concerned with the elicitation, analysis, specification, and validation of software requirements as well as the management of requirements during the whole life cycle of the software product

A. How good do you regard your Requirements Analysis and Specification skills? *

i This element is only shown when the option "Yes" is selected in the question "Are you currently a student in the third year of the Informatics study programme?"

- Very poor
- Poor
- Average
- Good
- Very good
- I do not know
- I do not understand the question enough to answer

B. How much of the knowledge that you currently have, you have acquired in the courses and projects of the University? *

i This element is only shown when the option "Very good", "Good", "Average" or "Poor" is selected in the question "A. How good do you regard your Requirements Analysis and Specification skills?"

- None of the knowledge
- A small amount
- Average
- Most of the knowledge
- All of the knowledge
- I do not know
- I do not understand the question enough to answer

C. How important for your position is this Knowledge Area? *

 This element is only shown when the option "Yes" is selected in the question "Are you currently employed in a software company?"

- Not important
- Slightly important
- Moderately important
- Important
- Very important
- I do not know
- I do not understand the question enough to answer

D. How prepared are recent graduates (graduated bachelors in 2019, 2020, or 2021) in this KA? *

 This element is only shown when the option "Yes" is selected in the question "Are you currently employed in a software company?"

- Unprepared
- Slightly prepared
- Moderately prepared
- Prepared
- Very prepared
- I do not know
- I do not understand the question enough to answer

 Page break

Page 4

Mandatory fields are marked with a star *

2. Software Design

The process of defining the architecture, components, interfaces, and other characteristics of a system or component and the result of that process

2.1. Design fundamentals

Knowledge of principles, strategies and patterns in designing a software architecture (Abstraction, Coupling, Decomposition, Separation of concerns etc.)

A. How good do you regard your Design fundamentals skills? *

i This element is only shown when the option "Yes" is selected in the question "Are you currently a student in the third year of the Informatics study programme?"

- Very poor
- Poor
- Average
- Good
- Very good
- I do not know
- I do not understand the question enough to answer

B. How much of the knowledge that you currently have, you have acquired in the courses and projects of the University? *

i This element is only shown when the option "Very good", "Good", "Average" or "Poor" is selected in the question "A. How good do you regard your Design fundamentals skills?"

- None of the knowledge
- A small amount
- Average
- Most of the knowledge
- All of the knowledge
- I do not know
- I do not understand the question enough to answer

C. How important for your position is this Knowledge Area? *

i This element is only shown when the option "Yes" is selected in the question "Are you currently employed in a software company?"

- Not important
- Slightly important
- Moderately important
- Important
- Very important
- I do not know
- I do not understand the question enough to answer

D. How prepared are recent graduates (graduated bachelors in 2019, 2020, or 2021) in this KA? *

i This element is only shown when the option "Yes" is selected in the question "Are you currently employed in a software company?"

- Unprepared
- Slightly prepared
- Moderately prepared
- Prepared
- Very prepared
- I do not know
- I do not understand the question enough to answer

2.2. Key issues in design

Knowledge of issues in software design that impact the entire software system, not just a module, or component (Security, Concurrency, Data persistence, Error handling etc.)

A. How good do you regard your Key issues in design skills? *

i This element is only shown when the option "Yes" is selected in the question "Are you currently a student in the third year of the Informatics study programme?"

- Very poor
- Poor
- Average
- Good
- Very good
- I do not know
- I do not understand the question enough to answer

B. How much of the knowledge that you currently have, you have acquired in the courses and projects of the University? *

i This element is only shown when the option "Very good", "Good", "Average" or "Poor" is selected in the question "A. How good do you regard your Key issues in design skills?"

- None of the knowledge
- A small amount
- Average
- Most of the knowledge
- All of the knowledge
- I do not know
- I do not understand the question enough to answer

C. How important for your position is this Knowledge Area? *

i This element is only shown when the option "Yes" is selected in the question "Are you currently employed in a software company?"

- Not important
- Slightly important
- Moderately important
- Important
- Very important
- I do not know
- I do not understand the question enough to answer

D. How prepared are recent graduates (graduated bachelors in 2019, 2020, or 2021) in this KA? *

i This element is only shown when the option "Yes" is selected in the question "Are you currently employed in a software company?"

- Unprepared
- Slightly prepared
- Moderately prepared
- Prepared
- Very prepared
- I do not know
- I do not understand the question enough to answer

2.3. Software Structure and Architecture

Knowledge of software structures and architecture patterns (Architectural Styles - MVC, MVVC, Client-Server, Broker etc.; Design patterns - Singleton, Decorator, Factory, State etc.)

A. How good do you regard your Software Structure and Architecture skills? *

i This element is only shown when the option "Yes" is selected in the question "Are you currently a student in the third year of the Informatics study programme?"

- Very poor
- Poor
- Average
- Good
- Very good
- I do not know
- I do not understand the question enough to answer

B. How much of the knowledge that you currently have, you have acquired in the courses and projects of the University? *

i This element is only shown when the option "Very good", "Good", "Average" or "Poor" is selected in the question "A. How good do you regard your Software Structure and Architecture skills?"

- None of the knowledge
- A small amount
- Average
- Most of the knowledge
- All of the knowledge
- I do not know
- I do not understand the question enough to answer

C. How important for your position is this Knowledge Area? *

i This element is only shown when the option "Yes" is selected in the question "Are you currently employed in a software company?"

- Not important
- Slightly important
- Moderately important
- Important
- Very important
- I do not know
- I do not understand the question enough to answer

D. How prepared are recent graduates (graduated bachelors in 2019, 2020, or 2021) in this KA? *

i This element is only shown when the option "Yes" is selected in the question "Are you currently employed in a software company?"

- Unprepared
- Slightly prepared
- Moderately prepared
- Prepared
- Very prepared
- I do not know
- I do not understand the question enough to answer

2.4. User Interface Design

Knowledge of principles, issues and modalities of implementing a User Interface (Principles - Learnability, Recoverability, Familiarity, Diversity etc.; Modalities - Menu selection, Form fill-in, Question-Answer etc.)

A. How good do you regard your User Interface Design skills? *

i This element is only shown when the option "Yes" is selected in the question "Are you currently a student in the third year of the Informatics study programme?"

- Very poor
- Poor
- Average
- Good
- Very good
- I do not know
- I do not understand the question enough to answer

B. How much of the knowledge that you currently have, you have acquired in the courses and projects of the University? *

i This element is only shown when the option "Very good", "Good", "Average" or "Poor" is selected in the question "A. How good do you regard your User Interface Design skills?"

- None of the knowledge
- A small amount
- Average
- Most of the knowledge
- All of the knowledge
- I do not know
- I do not understand the question enough to answer

C. How important for your position is this Knowledge Area? *

i This element is only shown when the option "Yes" is selected in the question "Are you currently employed in a software company?"

- Not important
- Slightly important
- Moderately important
- Important
- Very important
- I do not know
- I do not understand the question enough to answer

D. How prepared are recent graduates (graduated bachelors in 2019, 2020, or 2021) in this KA? *

i This element is only shown when the option "Yes" is selected in the question "Are you currently employed in a software company?"

- Unprepared
- Slightly prepared
- Moderately prepared
- Prepared
- Very prepared
- I do not know
- I do not understand the question enough to answer

2.5. Design quality analysis and evaluation

Knowledge of using and measuring the qualities of a software's architecture (Software Qualities - Maintainability, Portability, Testability, Usability etc.)

A. How good do you regard your Design quality analysis and evaluation skills? *

i This element is only shown when the option "Yes" is selected in the question "Are you currently a student in the third year of the Informatics study programme?"

- Very poor
- Poor
- Average
- Good
- Very good
- I do not know
- I do not understand the question enough to answer

B. How much of the knowledge that you currently have, you have acquired in the courses and projects of the University? *

i This element is only shown when the option "Poor", "Very good", "Good" or "Average" is selected in the question "A. How good do you regard your Design quality analysis and evaluation skills?"

- None of the knowledge
- A small amount
- Average
- Most of the knowledge
- All of the knowledge
- I do not know
- I do not understand the question enough to answer

C. How important for your position is this Knowledge Area? *

i This element is only shown when the option "Yes" is selected in the question "Are you currently employed in a software company?"

- Not important
- Slightly important
- Moderately important
- Important
- Very important
- I do not know
- I do not understand the question enough to answer

D. How prepared are recent graduates (graduated bachelors in 2019, 2020, or 2021) in this KA? *

i This element is only shown when the option "Yes" is selected in the question "Are you currently employed in a software company?"

- Unprepared
- Slightly prepared
- Moderately prepared
- Prepared
- Very prepared
- I do not know
- I do not understand the question enough to answer

2.6. Software Design Notation

Knowledge of using notations like UML diagrams, ERD diagrams, Pseudo-Code, Data-flow Diagrams etc.

A. How good do you regard your Software Design Notation skills? *

i This element is only shown when the option "Yes" is selected in the question "Are you currently a student in the third year of the Informatics study programme?"

- Very poor
- Poor
- Average
- Good
- Very good
- I do not know
- I do not understand the question enough to answer

B. How much of the knowledge that you currently have, you have acquired in the courses and projects of the University? *

i This element is only shown when the option "Very good", "Good", "Average" or "Poor" is selected in the question "A. How good do you regard your Software Design Notation skills?"

- None of the knowledge
- A small amount
- Average
- Most of the knowledge
- All of the knowledge
- I do not know
- I do not understand the question enough to answer

C. How important for your position is this Knowledge Area? *

i This element is only shown when the option "Yes" is selected in the question "Are you currently employed in a software company?"

- Not important
- Slightly important
- Moderately important
- Important
- Very important
- I do not know
- I do not understand the question enough to answer

D. How prepared are recent graduates (graduated bachelors in 2019, 2020, or 2021) in this KA? *

i This element is only shown when the option "Yes" is selected in the question "Are you currently employed in a software company?"

- Unprepared
- Slightly prepared
- Moderately prepared
- Prepared
- Very prepared
- I do not know
- I do not understand the question enough to answer

2.7. Software Design Strategy and Methods

Knowledge of using different strategies and methods of software design like Object-Oriented Design, Function-Oriented Design, Data-Structure Design, Component-Based Design

A. How good do you regard your Software Design Strategy and Methods skills? *

i This element is only shown when the option "Yes" is selected in the question "Are you currently a student in the third year of the Informatics study programme?"

- Very poor
- Poor
- Average
- Good
- Very good
- I do not know
- I do not understand the question enough to answer

B. How much of the knowledge that you currently have, you have acquired in the courses and projects of the University? *

i This element is only shown when the option "Good", "Average", "Poor" or "Very good" is selected in the question "A. How good do you regard your Software Design Strategy and Methods skills?"

- None of the knowledge
- A small amount
- Average
- Most of the knowledge
- All of the knowledge
- I do not know
- I do not understand the question enough to answer

C. How important for your position is this Knowledge Area? *

i This element is only shown when the option "Yes" is selected in the question "Are you currently employed in a software company?"

- Not important
- Slightly important
- Moderately important
- Important
- Very important
- I do not know
- I do not understand the question enough to answer

D. How prepared are recent graduates (graduated bachelors in 2019, 2020, or 2021) in this KA? *

i This element is only shown when the option "Yes" is selected in the question "Are you currently employed in a software company?"

- Unprepared
- Slightly prepared
- Moderately prepared
- Prepared
- Very prepared
- I do not know
- I do not understand the question enough to answer

2.8. Design tools

Knowledge of using different tools specific to software design like Diagram Tools (Draw.IO etc.), Wireframing apps (Adobe XD, Figma etc.), Planning apps (MS Project, ReadTheDocs, Outline etc.)

A. How good do you regard your Design tools skills? *

i This element is only shown when the option "Yes" is selected in the question "Are you currently a student in the third year of the Informatics study programme?"

- Very poor
- Poor
- Average
- Good
- Very good
- I do not know
- I do not understand the question enough to answer

B. How much of the knowledge that you currently have, you have acquired in the courses and projects of the University? *

i This element is only shown when the option "Very good", "Good", "Average" or "Poor" is selected in the question "A. How good do you regard your Design tools skills?"

- None of the knowledge
- A small amount
- Average
- Most of the knowledge
- All of the knowledge
- I do not know
- I do not understand the question enough to answer

C. How important for your position is this Knowledge Area? *

 This element is only shown when the option "Yes" is selected in the question "Are you currently employed in a software company?"

- Not important
- Slightly important
- Moderately important
- Important
- Very important
- I do not know
- I do not understand the question enough to answer

D. How prepared are recent graduates (graduated bachelors in 2019, 2020, or 2021) in this KA? *

 This element is only shown when the option "Yes" is selected in the question "Are you currently employed in a software company?"

- Unprepared
- Slightly prepared
- Moderately prepared
- Prepared
- Very prepared
- I do not know
- I do not understand the question enough to answer

 Page break

Page 5

Mandatory fields are marked with a star *

3. Software Construction

Knowledge in creating working software through a combination of coding, verification, unit testing, integration testing, and debugging, and in general implementing the provided software design

A. How good do you regard your Software Construction skills? *

i This element is only shown when the option "Yes" is selected in the question "Are you currently a student in the third year of the Informatics study programme?"

- Very poor
- Poor
- Average
- Good
- Very good
- I do not know
- I do not understand the question enough to answer

B. How much of the knowledge that you currently have, you have acquired in the courses and projects of the University? *

i This element is only shown when the option "Very good", "Good", "Average" or "Poor" is selected in the question "A. How good do you regard your Software Construction skills?"

- None of the knowledge
- A small amount
- Average
- Most of the knowledge
- All of the knowledge
- I do not know
- I do not understand the question enough to answer

C. How important for your position is this Knowledge Area? *

 This element is only shown when the option "Yes" is selected in the question "Are you currently employed in a software company?"

- Not important
- Slightly important
- Moderately important
- Important
- Very important
- I do not know
- I do not understand the question enough to answer

D. How prepared are recent graduates (graduated bachelors in 2019, 2020, or 2021) in this KA? *

 This element is only shown when the option "Yes" is selected in the question "Are you currently employed in a software company?"

- Unprepared
- Slightly prepared
- Moderately prepared
- Prepared
- Very prepared
- I do not know
- I do not understand the question enough to answer

 Page break

Page 6

Mandatory fields are marked with a star *

4. Testing

Knowledge in designing test cases throughout the entire planning, development and maintenance life cycle stages.

4.1. Testing Fundamentals

Knowledge in specific terminology (Faults vs. Failures, Test Selection, Effectiveness, Discovery etc.)

A. How good do you regard your Testing Fundamentals skills? *

i This element is only shown when the option "Yes" is selected in the question "Are you currently a student in the third year of the Informatics study programme?"

- Very poor
- Poor
- Average
- Good
- Very good
- I do not know
- I do not understand the question enough to answer

B. How much of the knowledge that you currently have, you have acquired in the courses and projects of the University? *

i This element is only shown when the option "Very good", "Good", "Average" or "Poor" is selected in the question "A. How good do you regard your Testing Fundamentals skills?"

- None of the knowledge
- A small amount
- Average
- Most of the knowledge
- All of the knowledge
- I do not know
- I do not understand the question enough to answer

C. How important for your position is this Knowledge Area? *

i This element is only shown when the option "Yes" is selected in the question "Are you currently employed in a software company?"

- Not important
- Slightly important
- Moderately important
- Important
- Very important
- I do not know
- I do not understand the question enough to answer

D. How prepared are recent graduates (graduated bachelors in 2019, 2020, or 2021) in this KA? *

i This element is only shown when the option "Yes" is selected in the question "Are you currently employed in a software company?"

- Unprepared
- Slightly prepared
- Moderately prepared
- Prepared
- Very prepared
- I do not know
- I do not understand the question enough to answer

4.2. Test Levels

Knowledge of designing tests on different levels (Unit Tests, Integration Tests, End-to-End tests, System Test, Performance tests, Stress tests, Security tests etc..)

A. How good do you regard your Test Levels skills? *

i This element is only shown when the option "Yes" is selected in the question "Are you currently a student in the third year of the Informatics study programme?"

- Very poor
- Poor
- Average
- Good
- Very good
- I do not know
- I do not understand the question enough to answer

B. How much of the knowledge that you currently have, you have acquired in the courses and projects of the University? *

i This element is only shown when the option "Very good", "Good", "Average" or "Poor" is selected in the question "A. How good do you regard your Test Levels skills?"

- None of the knowledge
- A small amount
- Average
- Most of the knowledge
- All of the knowledge
- I do not know
- I do not understand the question enough to answer

C. How important for your position is this Knowledge Area? *

i This element is only shown when the option "Yes" is selected in the question "Are you currently employed in a software company?"

- Not important
- Slightly important
- Moderately important
- Important
- Very important
- I do not know
- I do not understand the question enough to answer

D. How prepared are recent graduates (graduated bachelors in 2019, 2020, or 2021) in this KA? *

i This element is only shown when the option "Yes" is selected in the question "Are you currently employed in a software company?"

- Unprepared
- Slightly prepared
- Moderately prepared
- Prepared
- Very prepared
- I do not know
- I do not understand the question enough to answer

4.3. Test Techniques

Knowledge of designing tests using different techniques (Exploratory testing, Input Domain based testing, Code-based testing, Data Flow based testing, Usage based testing etc.)

A. How good do you regard your Test Techniques skills? *

i This element is only shown when the option "Yes" is selected in the question "Are you currently a student in the third year of the Informatics study programme?"

- Very poor
- Poor
- Average
- Good
- Very good
- I do not know
- I do not understand the question enough to answer

B. How much of the knowledge that you currently have, you have acquired in the courses and projects of the University? *

i This element is only shown when the option "Very good", "Good", "Average" or "Poor" is selected in the question "A. How good do you regard your Test Techniques skills?"

- None of the knowledge
- A small amount
- Average
- Most of the knowledge
- All of the knowledge
- I do not know
- I do not understand the question enough to answer

C. How important for your position is this Knowledge Area? *

i This element is only shown when the option "Yes" is selected in the question "Are you currently employed in a software company?"

- Not important
- Slightly important
- Moderately important
- Important
- Very important
- I do not know
- I do not understand the question enough to answer

D. How prepared are recent graduates (graduated bachelors in 2019, 2020, or 2021) in this KA? *

i This element is only shown when the option "Yes" is selected in the question "Are you currently employed in a software company?"

- Unprepared
- Slightly prepared
- Moderately prepared
- Prepared
- Very prepared
- I do not know
- I do not understand the question enough to answer

4.4. Test Related Measures

Knowledge of using measurements in testing(Fault types, Classification, Statistics, Reliability Evaluation, Comparison and Relative Effectiveness)

A. How good do you regard your Test Related Measures skills? *

i This element is only shown when the option "Yes" is selected in the question "Are you currently a student in the third year of the Informatics study programme?"

- Very poor
- Poor
- Average
- Good
- Very good
- I do not know
- I do not understand the question enough to answer

B. How much of the knowledge that you currently have, you have acquired in the courses and projects of the University? *

i This element is only shown when the option "Very good", "Good", "Average" or "Poor" is selected in the question "A. How good do you regard your Test Related Measures skills?"

- None of the knowledge
- A small amount
- Average
- Most of the knowledge
- All of the knowledge
- I do not know
- I do not understand the question enough to answer

C. How important for your position is this Knowledge Area? *

i This element is only shown when the option "Yes" is selected in the question "Are you currently employed in a software company?"

- Not important
- Slightly important
- Moderately important
- Important
- Very important
- I do not know
- I do not understand the question enough to answer

D. How prepared are recent graduates (graduated bachelors in 2019, 2020, or 2021) in this KA? *

i This element is only shown when the option "Yes" is selected in the question "Are you currently employed in a software company?"

- Unprepared
- Slightly prepared
- Moderately prepared
- Prepared
- Very prepared
- I do not know
- I do not understand the question enough to answer

4.5. Test Process

Knowledge in creating a testing process, documentation, implementing Test-Driven Development, Test Reuse, Test Patterns, Test Tracking

A. How good do you regard your Test Process skills? *

i This element is only shown when the option "Yes" is selected in the question "Are you currently a student in the third year of the Informatics study programme?"

- Very poor
- Poor
- Average
- Good
- Very good
- I do not know
- I do not understand the question enough to answer

B. How much of the knowledge that you currently have, you have acquired in the courses and projects of the University? *

i This element is only shown when the option "Very good", "Good", "Average" or "Poor" is selected in the question "A. How good do you regard your Test Process skills?"

- None of the knowledge
- A small amount
- Average
- Most of the knowledge
- All of the knowledge
- I do not know
- I do not understand the question enough to answer

C. How important for your position is this Knowledge Area? *

i This element is only shown when the option "Yes" is selected in the question "Are you currently employed in a software company?"

- Not important
- Slightly important
- Moderately important
- Important
- Very important
- I do not know
- I do not understand the question enough to answer

D. How prepared are recent graduates (graduated bachelors in 2019, 2020, or 2021) in this KA? *

i This element is only shown when the option "Yes" is selected in the question "Are you currently employed in a software company?"

- Unprepared
- Slightly prepared
- Moderately prepared
- Prepared
- Very prepared
- I do not know
- I do not understand the question enough to answer

4.6. Software Testing Tools

Knowledge of using various testing Tools (Coverage analyzers, test generators, bug tracers etc.)

A. How good do you regard your Software Testing Tools skills? *

i This element is only shown when the option "Yes" is selected in the question "Are you currently a student in the third year of the Informatics study programme?"

- Very poor
- Poor
- Average
- Good
- Very good
- I do not know
- I do not understand the question enough to answer

B. How much of the knowledge that you currently have, you have acquired in the courses and projects of the University? *

i This element is only shown when the option "Very good", "Good", "Average" or "Poor" is selected in the question "A. How good do you regard your Software Testing Tools skills?"

- None of the knowledge
- A small amount
- Average
- Most of the knowledge
- All of the knowledge
- I do not know
- I do not understand the question enough to answer

C. How important for your position is this Knowledge Area? *

 This element is only shown when the option "Yes" is selected in the question "Are you currently employed in a software company?"

- Not important
- Slightly important
- Moderately important
- Important
- Very important
- I do not know
- I do not understand the question enough to answer

D. How prepared are recent graduates (graduated bachelors in 2019, 2020, or 2021) in this KA? *

 This element is only shown when the option "Yes" is selected in the question "Are you currently employed in a software company?"

- Unprepared
- Slightly prepared
- Moderately prepared
- Prepared
- Very prepared
- I do not know
- I do not understand the question enough to answer

 Page break

Page 7

Mandatory fields are marked with a star *

5. Software Engineering Management

5.1 Project initiation and scope definition

Knowledge and experience with activities in gathering software requirements and the assessment of project feasibility

A. How good do you regard your Project initiation and scope definition skills? *

i This element is only shown when the option "Yes" is selected in the question "Are you currently a student in the third year of the Informatics study programme?"

- Very poor
- Poor
- Average
- Good
- Very good
- I do not know
- I do not understand the question enough to answer

B. How much of the knowledge that you currently have, you have acquired in the courses and projects of the University? *

i This element is only shown when the option "Very good", "Good", "Average" or "Poor" is selected in the question "A. How good do you regard your Project initiation and scope definition skills?"

- None of the knowledge
- A small amount
- Average
- Most of the knowledge
- All of the knowledge
- I do not know
- I do not understand the question enough to answer

C. How important for your position is this Knowledge Area? *

i This element is only shown when the option "Yes" is selected in the question "Are you currently employed in a software company?"

- Not important
- Slightly important
- Moderately important
- Important
- Very important
- I do not know
- I do not understand the question enough to answer

D. How prepared are recent graduates (graduated bachelors in 2019, 2020, or 2021) in this KA? *

i This element is only shown when the option "Yes" is selected in the question "Are you currently employed in a software company?"

- Unprepared
- Slightly prepared
- Moderately prepared
- Prepared
- Very prepared
- I do not know
- I do not understand the question enough to answer

5.2 Software Project Planning

Knowledge in planning the Software Development Life Cycle, Determining Deliverables; Effort, Cost and Resources Estimation; Risk Management

A. How good do you regard your Software Project Planning skills? *

i This element is only shown when the option "Yes" is selected in the question "Are you currently a student in the third year of the Informatics study programme?"

- Very poor
- Poor
- Average
- Good
- Very good
- I do not know
- I do not understand the question enough to answer

B. How much of the knowledge that you currently have, you have acquired in the courses and projects of the University? *

i This element is only shown when the option "Very good", "Good", "Average" or "Poor" is selected in the question "A. How good do you regard your Software Project Planning skills?"

- None of the knowledge
- A small amount
- Average
- Most of the knowledge
- All of the knowledge
- I do not know
- I do not understand the question enough to answer

C. How important for your position is this Knowledge Area? *

 This element is only shown when the option "Yes" is selected in the question "Are you currently employed in a software company?"

- Not important
- Slightly important
- Moderately important
- Important
- Very important
- I do not know
- I do not understand the question enough to answer

D. How prepared are recent graduates (graduated bachelors in 2019, 2020, or 2021) in this KA? *

 This element is only shown when the option "Yes" is selected in the question "Are you currently employed in a software company?"

- Unprepared
- Slightly prepared
- Moderately prepared
- Prepared
- Very prepared
- I do not know
- I do not understand the question enough to answer

5.3 Software Project Enactment

Knowledge in implementing the plan, monitoring the software development process, and reporting.

A. How good do you regard your Software Project Enactment skills? *

i This element is only shown when the option "Yes" is selected in the question "Are you currently a student in the third year of the Informatics study programme?"

- Very poor
- Poor
- Average
- Good
- Very good
- I do not know
- I do not understand the question enough to answer

B. How much of the knowledge that you currently have, you have acquired in the courses and projects of the University? *

i This element is only shown when the option "Very good", "Good", "Average" or "Poor" is selected in the question "A. How good do you regard your Software Project Enactment skills?"

- None of the knowledge
- A small amount
- Average
- Most of the knowledge
- All of the knowledge
- I do not know
- I do not understand the question enough to answer

C. How important for your position is this Knowledge Area? *

i This element is only shown when the option "Yes" is selected in the question "Are you currently employed in a software company?"

- Not important
- Slightly important
- Moderately important
- Important
- Very important
- I do not know
- I do not understand the question enough to answer

D. How prepared are recent graduates (graduated bachelors in 2019, 2020, or 2021) in this KA? *

i This element is only shown when the option "Yes" is selected in the question "Are you currently employed in a software company?"

- Unprepared
- Slightly prepared
- Moderately prepared
- Prepared
- Very prepared
- I do not know
- I do not understand the question enough to answer

5.4 Review and Evaluation

Knowledge in determining satisfaction with the requirements, evaluation performance

A. How good do you regard your Review and Evaluation skills? *

i This element is only shown when the option "Yes" is selected in the question "Are you currently a student in the third year of the Informatics study programme?"

- Very poor
- Poor
- Average
- Good
- Very good
- I do not know
- I do not understand the question enough to answer

B. How much of the knowledge that you currently have, you have acquired in the courses and projects of the University? *

i This element is only shown when the option "Very good", "Good", "Average" or "Poor" is selected in the question "A. How good do you regard your Review and Evaluation skills?"

- None of the knowledge
- A small amount
- Average
- Most of the knowledge
- All of the knowledge
- I do not know
- I do not understand the question enough to answer

C. How important for your position is this Knowledge Area? *

i This element is only shown when the option "Yes" is selected in the question "Are you currently employed in a software company?"

- Not important
- Slightly important
- Moderately important
- Important
- Very important
- I do not know
- I do not understand the question enough to answer

D. How prepared are recent graduates (graduated bachelors in 2019, 2020, or 2021) in this KA? *

i This element is only shown when the option "Yes" is selected in the question "Are you currently employed in a software company?"

- Unprepared
- Slightly prepared
- Moderately prepared
- Prepared
- Very prepared
- I do not know
- I do not understand the question enough to answer

5.5 Closure

Knowledge in closing stages of the SDLC (Software Development Life Cycle).

A. How good do you regard your Closure skills? *

i This element is only shown when the option "Yes" is selected in the question "Are you currently a student in the third year of the Informatics study programme?"

- Very poor
- Poor
- Average
- Good
- Very good
- I do not know
- I do not understand the question enough to answer

B. How much of the knowledge that you currently have, you have acquired in the courses and projects of the University? *

i This element is only shown when the option "Very good", "Good", "Average" or "Poor" is selected in the question "A. How good do you regard your Closure skills?"

- None of the knowledge
- A small amount
- Average
- Most of the knowledge
- All of the knowledge
- I do not know
- I do not understand the question enough to answer

C. How important for your position is this Knowledge Area? *

i This element is only shown when the option "Yes" is selected in the question "Are you currently employed in a software company?"

- Not important
- Slightly important
- Moderately important
- Important
- Very important
- I do not know
- I do not understand the question enough to answer

D. How prepared are recent graduates (graduated bachelors in 2019, 2020, or 2021) in this KA? *

i This element is only shown when the option "Yes" is selected in the question "Are you currently employed in a software company?"

- Unprepared
- Slightly prepared
- Moderately prepared
- Prepared
- Very prepared
- I do not know
- I do not understand the question enough to answer

5.5 Software Engineering Measurement

Knowledge in measuring the performance, and evaluation of software objectives

A. How good do you regard your Software Engineering Measurement skills? *

i This element is only shown when the option "Yes" is selected in the question "Are you currently a student in the third year of the Informatics study programme?"

- Very poor
- Poor
- Average
- Good
- Very good
- I do not know
- I do not understand the question enough to answer

B. How much of the knowledge that you currently have, you have acquired in the courses and projects of the University? *

i This element is only shown when the option "Very good", "Good", "Average" or "Poor" is selected in the question "A. How good do you regard your Software Engineering Measurement skills?"

- None of the knowledge
- A small amount
- Average
- Most of the knowledge
- All of the knowledge
- I do not know
- I do not understand the question enough to answer

C. How important for your position is this Knowledge Area? *

i This element is only shown when the option "Yes" is selected in the question "Are you currently employed in a software company?"

- Not important
- Slightly important
- Moderately important
- Important
- Very important
- I do not know
- I do not understand the question enough to answer

D. How prepared are recent graduates (graduated bachelors in 2019, 2020, or 2021) in this KA? *

i This element is only shown when the option "Yes" is selected in the question "Are you currently employed in a software company?"

- Unprepared
- Slightly prepared
- Moderately prepared
- Prepared
- Very prepared
- I do not know
- I do not understand the question enough to answer

5.5 Software Engineering Management Tools

Knowledge in using SE Management Tools (Planning and Tracking - Trello, Jira, Monday etc., Communication - Slack, Teams, etc. Measurement - Analytics tools)

A. How good do you regard your Software Engineering Management Tools skills? *

i This element is only shown when the option "Yes" is selected in the question "Are you currently a student in the third year of the Informatics study programme?"

- Very poor
- Poor
- Average
- Good
- Very good
- I do not know
- I do not understand the question enough to answer

B. How much of the knowledge that you currently have, you have acquired in the courses and projects of the University? *

i This element is only shown when the option "Very good", "Good", "Average" or "Poor" is selected in the question "A. How good do you regard your Software Engineering Management Tools skills?"

- None of the knowledge
- A small amount
- Average
- Most of the knowledge
- All of the knowledge
- I do not know
- I do not understand the question enough to answer

C. How important for your position is this Knowledge Area? *

 This element is only shown when the option "Yes" is selected in the question "Are you currently employed in a software company?"

- Not important
- Slightly important
- Moderately important
- Important
- Very important
- I do not know
- I do not understand the question enough to answer

D. How prepared are recent graduates (graduated bachelors in 2019, 2020, or 2021) in this KA? *

 This element is only shown when the option "Yes" is selected in the question "Are you currently employed in a software company?"

- Unprepared
- Slightly prepared
- Moderately prepared
- Prepared
- Very prepared
- I do not know
- I do not understand the question enough to answer

 Page break

Page 8

Mandatory fields are marked with a star *

6. Software Engineering Process

Knowledge in assessing and improving the SDLC (Software Development Life Cycle) stages, software process measurements. Giving, receiving, and using technical feedback.

A. How good do you regard your Software Engineering Process skills? *

i This element is only shown when the option "Yes" is selected in the question "Are you currently a student in the third year of the Informatics study programme?"

- Very poor
- Poor
- Average
- Good
- Very good
- I do not know
- I do not understand the question enough to answer

B. How much of the knowledge that you currently have, you have acquired in the courses and projects of the University? *

i This element is only shown when the option "Very good", "Good", "Average" or "Poor" is selected in the question "A. How good do you regard your Software Engineering Process skills?"

- None of the knowledge
- A small amount
- Average
- Most of the knowledge
- All of the knowledge
- I do not know
- I do not understand the question enough to answer

C. How important for your position is this Knowledge Area? *

i This element is only shown when the option "Yes" is selected in the question "Are you currently employed in a software company?"

- Not important
- Slightly important
- Moderately important
- Important
- Very important
- I do not know
- I do not understand the question enough to answer

D. How prepared are recent graduates (graduated bachelors in 2019, 2020, or 2021) in this KA? *

i This element is only shown when the option "Yes" is selected in the question "Are you currently employed in a software company?"

- Unprepared
- Slightly prepared
- Moderately prepared
- Prepared
- Very prepared
- I do not know
- I do not understand the question enough to answer

7. Software Engineering Quality

Knowledge in delivering under the specified conditions which were established in the requirements gathering and analysis steps.

A. How good do you regard your Software Engineering Quality skills? *

i This element is only shown when the option "Yes" is selected in the question "Are you currently a student in the third year of the Informatics study programme?"

- Very poor
- Poor
- Average
- Good
- Very good
- I do not know
- I do not understand the question enough to answer

B. How much of the knowledge that you currently have, you have acquired in the courses and projects of the University? *

i This element is only shown when the option "Very good", "Good", "Average" or "Poor" is selected in the question "A. How good do you regard your Software Engineering Quality skills?"

- None of the knowledge
- A small amount
- Average
- Most of the knowledge
- All of the knowledge
- I do not know
- I do not understand the question enough to answer

C. How important for your position is this Knowledge Area? *

i This element is only shown when the option "Yes" is selected in the question "Are you currently employed in a software company?"

- Not important
- Slightly important
- Moderately important
- Important
- Very important
- I do not know
- I do not understand the question enough to answer

D. How prepared are recent graduates (graduated bachelors in 2019, 2020, or 2021) in this KA? *

i This element is only shown when the option "Yes" is selected in the question "Are you currently employed in a software company?"

- Unprepared
- Slightly prepared
- Moderately prepared
- Prepared
- Very prepared
- I do not know
- I do not understand the question enough to answer

8. Software Engineering Professional Practice

Knowledge and abilities in conducting services in order to achieve certain standards or criteria in both the process of development and the end product. This includes both technical and non-technical aspects – professionalism, group dynamics, communication skills

A. How good do you regard your Software Engineering Professional Practice skills? *

i This element is only shown when the option "Yes" is selected in the question "Are you currently a student in the third year of the Informatics study programme?"

- Very poor
- Poor
- Average
- Good
- Very good
- I do not know
- I do not understand the question enough to answer

B. How much of the knowledge that you currently have, you have acquired in the courses and projects of the University? *

i This element is only shown when the option "Poor", "Very good", "Good" or "Average" is selected in the question "A. How good do you regard your Software Engineering Professional Practice skills?"

- None of the knowledge
- A small amount
- Average
- Most of the knowledge
- All of the knowledge
- I do not know
- I do not understand the question enough to answer

C. How important for your position is this Knowledge Area? *

 This element is only shown when the option "Yes" is selected in the question "Are you currently employed in a software company?"

- Not important
- Slightly important
- Moderately important
- Important
- Very important
- I do not know
- I do not understand the question enough to answer

D. How prepared are recent graduates (graduated bachelors in 2019, 2020, or 2021) in this KA? *

 This element is only shown when the option "Yes" is selected in the question "Are you currently employed in a software company?"

- Unprepared
- Slightly prepared
- Moderately prepared
- Prepared
- Very prepared
- I do not know
- I do not understand the question enough to answer

 Page break

Mandatory fields are marked with a star *

Last questions

I understood the question topics, and the language of the survey *

This question aims to find out your understanding of the topics of the survey, and other obstacles that you may have had in filling this questionnaire.

Totally disagree

Disagree

Undecided

Agree

Totally Agree

Would you like to leave some feedback on this survey?

[See recent changes in Nettskjema](#)

